

ISSN 2249-605X

SLRF Impact Factor 2.361

15 Days

**An International Refereed & Peer-Reviewed Research
Journal Related to Higher Education for all Subjects**

Volume 155 15 January 2018
UGC Approved

प्रधान संपादक
डॉ० मुकेश कुमार मालवीय
Email - researcha2z@gmail.com
Cell: 08004851126

15Days

An International Research Refereed Journal Related
to Higher Education for all Subject. Vol.155 Jan.2018

EDITOR IN CHIEF

MUKESH KUMAR MALVIYA
ASST. PROFESSOR
LAW SCHOOL, BHU, VARANASI (U. P.)
MO. +91-8004851126

SPECIAL MEMBER OF ADMINISTRATION

SHRI SHYAM BABU PATEL DEPUTY REGISTRAR
& CAO (SSH) BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY VARANASI

MEMBERS OF EDITORIAL BOARD

DR. MONA PUROHIT HOD, LAW DEPARTMENT,
BU, BHOPAL.
DR. ARCHANA RANKA HOD, SCHOOL OF LAW,
DAVV, INDORE.
SHRI P.P.SINSH, HOD, LAW DEPARTMENT,
DR.HSGVV SAGAR.
DR.AMRENDRA KUMAR MISHRA HOD, LAW
DEPARTMENT, DDU GORAKHPUR.
DR. SHEPHALI YADAV HOD, LAW DEPARTMENT,
MJPRV, BAREILLY.
DR. VANI BHUSHAN FORMER HOD, PG
DEPARTMENT OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF PATNA.
DR. J.K.JAIN PRINCIPAL NEW GOVT. LAW
COLLEGE, INDORE.
DR. R.K. MURALI ASSO. PROFESSOR, LAW
SCHOOL, BHU, VARANASI.
DR. AHMED NASEEM, ASST. PROFESSOR, LAW
DEPARTMENT, DDU, GORAKHPUR.
SHRI ROSHAN LAL ASST. PROFESSOR, LAW
DEPARTMENT, UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD.

PATRON

PROFESSOR SUKHPAL SINGH
VICE CHANCELLOR, HIDAYATULLAH NATIONAL
LAW UNIVERSITY, RAIPUR.

SPECIAL RESEARCH SCHOLARS EDI. BOARD

PRIYANKA VAIDYA ASSISTANT PROFESSOR GOVT.
P. G. COLLEGE NALAGARH DISTT. SOLAN (H. P.)
SHRI RANA NAVNEET ROY JUNIOR RESEARCH
FELLOW, LAW SCHOOL, BHU, VARANASI.

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

DR. SANTOSH KUMAR TIWARI ASST. PROFESSOR
LAW FACULTY, NGB UNIVERSITY, ALLAHABAD.
DR. JADHAV SUNIL GULAB SINGH, ASST. PROFE,
YASHVANT COLLEGE, NADED, (MH).
DR. SAMTA JAIN ASST.PROFESSOR (ECONOMICS),
MATA GUJARI WOMENS COLLEGE, JABALPUR.
DR. AMIT KUMAR PANDEY HINDI DEPARTMENT,
BHU VARANASI.
DR. DEEPAK SHARMA ASST. PROFESSOR PKR JAIN
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, AMBALA CITY.
DR. SHARAD DHAR SHARMA SENIER RESEARCH
ASSOCIAT BHU VARANASI.
DR.SURENDRA PANDEY, DEPARTMENT OF HINDI,
BHU VARANASI.
SHRI SUNIL KUMAR LAW SCHOOL, BHU, VARANASI.
SHRI DILIP KUMAR ASST. PROFESSOR, LAW
FACULTY, NGB UNIVERSITY, ALLAHABAD.
KOMAL PRASAD YADAV ASST. PROFESSOR, LAW
FACULTY, NGB UNIVERSITY, ALLAHABAD.
KU. ANIMA SHUKLA ANUSHRI COLLEGE OF
NURSING, JABALPUR.

Vedic Period Gurukul vs Modern Period Google- The Two Varieties in the field of Education

***Prakash Chandra Mishra**

Assistant Professor in Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, U P-243006 INDIA

Email: prakashchandramishra075@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

The traditional Indian education system of “Gurukul” is based on Vedas. In the ancient times, education was mainly imparted through hearing and not writing. This system of education through lips and ears had the power to develop cognition, intelligence and strong memory. This Gurukul system of education has also been reflected through the Vedic literature had a very emotional training, use and practices of knowledge apart from providing socioeconomic and political training. This paper tries to focus on understanding the Gurukul system of education in India and linking this system of education through the scientific and modern education through Google. Whereas Present era, is the witness of advent of modern technologies and their application in almost all sector of economy and education is not an exception of this proven fact [1]. Online tutorials, courses, searching tools are the most common form of acquiring knowledge. There is a difference between Vidya and Shiksha. This sentence is capable enough to describe the significance of old Gurukul system of schooling and knowledge transferring. But what about wisdom that provides viveka of right and wrong (neer-ksheer vivek) which was the main object of ancient education system. Although present system of online education has certain specific features like 24x7, seamless operation, warehouses of knowledge are available in web world which were absent in conventional education method– Gurukul. This paper is an effort to understand the merits and demerits of both-Gurukula and Google system of learning. Paper further makes an attempt to find out the best way of learning, perceiving and sharing of knowledge.

Keywords: Gurukul, Character building, Gurukul Skill-based Education, Traditional Education System

1. INTRODUCTION

It was lord Rama in treta yuga and later lord Krishna in dwaparayuga, who gave great importance to Gurukul education. The environment of a Gurukul is very pure and filled with positive Sanskaras. A student in the Gurukul should pay his attention only to studies. If he directs his interest in many other things, his study will not be successful and he will not become learned and wise [2].

On the other hand, we have an American multinational technology company, Google. That specializes in internet related services and products. These include online advertising technologies, search, and cloud computing, software and hardware. In the next sections, a brief discussion has been made on Gurukul and Google education systems.

2. GURUKUL EDUCATION SYSYTEM

When anyone listen this old ancient word, then automatically one question will come in the mind. That is “What is Gurukul?” Let the discussion will be-

In ancient India, education was imparted through the Gurukul system. The students in a Gurukul system would offer services to the Guru and would follow strict discipline, live a moderate lifestyle and perpetually practice whatever education was imparted to the student by the Guru. Lord Shri Krishna, Lord

Rama, Maharana Pratap, Arjun etc, were the popular alumni of Gurukul system of education, who, despite coming from affluent family, studied with the poor people. A feeling of sensitivity and understanding develops in the student when they study in the heterogeneous group, which teaches the lessons of life for a successful journey ahead [3].

Fig.1: Spreading education through Gurukul Learning System [4]

The objectives of this form of education were:

- I. Discretion
- II. Improvement of character
- III. Generation of friendliness or social mindfulness
- IV. Fundamental personality development
- V. Proliferation of Virtue
- VI. Conservation of learning and culture

2.1. Merits of Gurukul System

- 1) The Gurukul system of education had distinctive features like enlightenment of pupils, transfer of knowledge rather than just sharing of information.
- 2) The Gurus had prodigious information and knew how to instruct the most burdensome of the things.
- 3) This Parampara used to take as much time as is needed and because of this, the students used to turn out in a meticulous form.
- 4) They used to attain a meticulous approach and inculcated high levels of competence
- 5) The student used to have high regard for the Guru and the discipline was sought offer.
- 6) Much of the education was realistic and there was bundle of benefit of this approach of learning.
- 7) The surroundings prearranged to the scholar ensured he would turn into an artisan or a skilful person in his field of interest.

2.2. Demerits of Gurukul System

- 1) The student did not get much exposure as he was under the tutelage of a single Guru.

- 2) There was no day and age designated for the course. The understudy needed to rely upon the educator entirely.
- 3) The old framework did not engage the hypothetical aspect of art.
- 4) The student additionally needed to perform everyday house chores for the master.

3. MAHABHARAT- A GOLDEN GURUKUL EDUCATION COURSE OF 18 DAYS DURATION

In the famous Indian historical great war of Mahabharat, the battle field named as Kurukshetra became instant Gurukul in which Lord Krishna became Guru and the one of the Pandav named Arjun from Panchupandav became his Shishya. Their conversation created the world largest religious book “Bhagbat Geeta”. Some conversation from Bhagbat Geeta may discuss here which can make people to understand the value of Gurukul. The 700 plus verses that Krishna taught Arjuna on the battlefield were later compiled into the Bhagavad Gita, a text that continues to be looked upon as the "Manual of Life". The Bhagavad Gita is today used by many organisations for better management and is even included in the syllabus of some business schools. Here are some excerpts from the Bhagavad Gita and how you can use them to resolve your own uncertainties, doubts, fears and confusions [5].

1) **Think with a calm mind:** Lord Krishna says: Undoubtedly, O Arjuna, the mind is restless and difficult to restrain, but it is subdued by any constant vigorous spiritual practice -- such as meditation -- with perseverance, and by detachment, O Arjuna (6.35). The first step to gaining clarity on any situation is developing a clear, calm and collected mind. This takes a lot of effort. One way is meditation, another is by distancing yourself from the situation - not physically but mentally - where you look at it as an outsider and have a bird's eye view of it. For example in the movie Vantage Point, the protagonist replays the same series of events of the crime in his mind, till he finally decodes the mystery. By distancing himself from the scene, he was no longer worried about his own life and could think objectively [6].

2) **Give up on results:** These are the most oft-repeated words of the Bhagavad Gita and often referred to as nishkam karma, doing action without expecting reward: You have control over doing your respective duty only, but no control or claim over the results. The fruits of work should not be your motive, and you should never be inactive (2.47). Most of our decisions get affected because we wonder about their outcomes and consequences. But when you realize that you have little control over the final outcome and when you don't focus on the gains, your efforts will be filled with more meaning. What's more you will also look at every gain as a bonus and appreciate the rewards more.

3) **Treat everyone equally:** A person is considered superior who is impartial towards companions, friends, enemies, neutrals, arbiters, haters, relatives, saints, and sinners (6.09). People make up our lives and it's difficult not to get influenced by them or by our equations with them. But that's exactly what Lord Krishna says. Treat everyone with the same lens of impartiality. A son shouldn't take on his father's business by virtue of being his son, but, because he is an able and competent worker. Likewise just because someone has picked a fight with you, don't write them off for good... the event isn't the person.

4) **Don't give in to stress:** In a world full of busyness and activity, with people snapping at each other, with road rage and intolerance, these words by Lord Krishna ring truer than ever: The one by whom others are not agitated and who is not agitated by others, who is free from joy, envy, fear, and anxiety, is also dear to Me (12.15). Rid yourself of excessive worry, don't take on more than you can cope with and add enough me-time in your day to help you de-stress. I often walk back home from work and just being by the sea, and watching its movements, helps me get rid of the tensions of the day.

5) **Be ready for change:** Arjuna, when inertia is predominant; ignorance, inactivity, carelessness, and delusion arise (14.13). Adding change and excitement to your activities helps give them a boost. Every once in a while, when you feel yourself slipping into lethargy or a state of inertia, stir yourself up, change

direction, give yourself a new challenge. I remember when I taught in a school, we'd often rearrange the way the children sat in class... we'd make them get up, move the tables around and sit in a new place. This kept them alert and also helped them make more friends. Similarly if you get stuck in one way of thinking, you're unlikely to come up with good solutions; be open to new views of learning and doing things.

6) **Act with conviction:** Whatever is done without faith - whether it is sacrifice, charity, austerity, or any other act -- is useless. It has no value here or hereafter, O Arjuna (17.28). There's a common story about villagers who had come out of their homes to pray for the much-awaited rain. Amid all these people, there was one small boy who had carried an umbrella. This little boy had true "faith". Setting out to do anything is an action, but being ready for it is faith. Before you undertake any action, think about how strongly you believe in it. If you don't need to justify it in anyway or draw on any extra reserves for it, then it's an act of conviction and the right decision for you.

7) **Set high standards:** Because whatever noble persons do, others follow. Whatever standard they set up, the world follows (3.21). Once you've decided on your course of action, set your own standards of excellence, benchmark your own success, and then create newer highs. The greatest achievers have kept pushing themselves for gaining greater levels of mastery. They compete with themselves and continue learning in all areas of their lives. They meet with success and failure but still keep growing. And their journeys continue to inspire us and give light to our lives.

4. GOOGLE EDUCATION SYSTEMS

Google means THOUSANDS ZERO-Putting thousands zero after 1. It Means Google can search on over the thousands topic within a minute. Search engine or portals have been around since the early days of the internet but it was Google, a relative latecomer that would go on to become the premier destination for finding just about anything on the World Wide Web. A search engine is a program that searches the Internet and finds web pages for the uses based on the keywords that you submit. These are several parts to a search engine, for instance [7]:

- Search engine software including Boolean operators, search fields, display format, etc.
- Spider software
- A database
- Algorithms that rank results for relevancy

Fig.2: Spreading education through Google Learning System[8]

Google was invented by computer scientist Larry Page and Sergey Brin. The site was named after Google- the name for the number 1 followed by 100 zeros found in the book "Mathematics and the Imagination" by Edward Kasner and James Newman. To the site's founders, the name represents the immense amount of information that a search engine has to sift through.

4.1 GOOGLE'S MISSION

In an interview with the Financial Times, Larry Page indicated Google is looking to capitalize on its success in its search business by staking claims in developing markets such as robotics, biotech and other industries that can have direct benefits to quality of life issues [6]. Page insisted in the interview that the company's societal goals are still primary, even though "We have not succeeded as much as we would like". Google's original mission statement was "to organize the world's information and make it universally accessible and useful". Its unofficial motto was "Don't be evil", a phrase which appears on its code of conduct page for employees and investors [7].

4.1.1 Ways Google gear Can Make learning more stimulating

Google is no stranger to the learning space. Teachers have been benefiting from the tools they create for years. Five ways of Google tools which can make education more exciting are as follows:

- 1) **Assign Students Expert Interviews with Google hangouts:** Several educators have used Google Hangouts to bring famous people and politicians into the classroom for lecturer or discussions. This helps them to be an expert on the subject of their choice and set up an interview with them our Google Hangouts.
- 2) **Teach students about marketing with Google sites:** Challenging students to create their own fictional business is a great way to get them thinking about economics, and entrepreneurship. They can work up business plans, create a budget, and get them thinking about marketing.
- 3) **Create a Google search scavenger hunt:** Everyone knows how to do Google search. Since Google is the main resource most people turn to for research, students should learn sooner rather than later how to find the most authoritative results within it.
- 4) **Have students map on educational road trip with Google Maps:** Google Maps can make it easy to identify important historical sites or other notable places and, with Google street view, can even give students a glimpse into what they look like on the ground.
- 5) **Use Google Drawing for collaborative image projects:** Many students are visual learners, so including some assignments based around images in your class can be a boon to the students who struggle more with text. This creates an opportunity for collaboration between students.

4.2 Merits of Google

Going Google in education is about four things:

- 1) **Empowerment:** Google is about being able to discover a world of infinite resources and change the role of the teacher from simply disseminating information to coaching and supporting students as they explore the information accessible to them to solve real world problems.
- 2) **Option:** Google helps to use the right device anytime, anywhere. With the help of this teachers and students use the right device whether it's a laptop, tablet, phone or desktop, regardless of platform and manufactures in school, at home or on the go.
- 3) **Collaboration:** Google helps in working together in real time. Using Google's collaboration productivity suite is often cited by educators as the most profound change in the way they teach and the way students learn. Collaboration fosters teamwork, problem solving and organization- key skills for the modern world.
- 4) **Range:** Google is affordable and easy to manage. Device and content management are equally important to keep the total cost of ownership low and allow it to learn efficiency and effectively manage all the different elements, from network to applicants to devices.

4.3 Demerits of Google

- 1) **Difficult account management:** Google Classroom doesn't allow access from multiple domains. Furthermore, you cannot log in with your personal Gmail to enter it; you need to be logged in Google Apps for Education. As a result, if you have already a personal Google ID, it may be frustrating to juggle multiple Google accounts. For example, if you have a Google document or a photo in your Gmail and you want to share it in the Google Classroom, you will need to save it separately in your computer's hard drive, log out, and then log in again with your Google Classroom account.
- 2) **Limited integration options:** Google Classroom hasn't yet integrated with Google Calendar, or any calendar whatsoever, which may cause some problems with organizing material and assignment deadlines.
- 3) **Too "Googlish":** First time Google users may get confused, as there are several buttons with icons familiar only to Google users. Additionally, despite enhanced integration between Google and YouTube, which significantly helps video sharing, support for other popular tools is not built in, and you may find it frustrating that you will need to, for example, convert a simple Word document to a Google Doc to work with. All in all, you will only find yourself comfortable in the Google Classroom environment as long as the tools you are using are aligned with Google services.
- 4) **No automated updates:** Activity feed doesn't update automatically, so learners will need to refresh regularly in order not to miss important announcements.
- 5) **Difficult learner sharing:** Learners cannot share their work with their peers, unless they become "owners" of a document, and even then they will need to approve sharing options, which will create a chaos if they want to share a document with their, say, 50+ classmates.
- 6) **Editing problems:** When you create an assignment and you distribute it to learners, learners become "owners" of the document and they are allowed to edit it. That means that they can delete any part of the assignment they want, which could cause problems, even if it happens accidentally.
- 7) **No automated quizzes and tests:** One of the main reasons that Google Classroom cannot yet fully replace your Learning Management System is that it doesn't provide automated quizzes and tests for your learners. In general, Google Classroom is more suitable for a blended learning experience than a fully online program.
- 8) **Impersonal:** Speaking of a blended learning environment, Google Classroom has not integrated Google Hangouts, which creates a problem; online interaction between teachers and learners is only possible through Google documents. Effective education requires interaction and building relationships with learners, and online discussions are the best way to achieve this in a virtual environment. Unfortunately, there is no way to have a live chat in Google Classroom; at least, again, not yet.

Fig.3: E-Learning through Google [10]

5. SANGHE SHAKTI KALYUGE!- NEED A COMBINATION OF BOTH

One or two people alone can't bring in a reform. A coming together is required. For that knowledge must dawn. So bring people to programs like this. Bring people together and do this work. What we do sometimes fails and if the failure repeats you can lose your courage. When we want to bring in reforms, even if we fail 10 times we should go ahead. We have to be so strong. Know that you will never be alone. Come together and work to increase awareness in society. Do satsangs. I will guide you constantly. (Stated by the great Indian spiritual leader Sri Sri Ravishankar) [8].

One needs to comprehend the reason for Gurukul: How it worked, what society resembled in the past and how the objective of Gurukul training can be accomplished in the present day setting. It is not just a case of copying the past. There must be an adjustment and a mix of both cutting edge instruction and convention if the Gurukul framework is to survive and affect today's general public. Gurukul education system provides students the knowledge about Hindu religion, brings close to nature, yogasanas, knowledge about practical situation of life etc. Google provides knowledge about technology, electronics, systems, latest software and tools etc. Modern education system has evolved with time and has been influenced by the changes and advance in technology. The education system has incorporated technologies like eBooks, video lectures distance learning through video chat demonstrations through 3-D imagery etc. There is no doubt that the system has evolved to incorporate the technological developments which includes involvement of Google in our lives. These have helped the student in grasping better knowledge through visual aids that helps in increasing retention. Teaching methods are continuously upgraded as per advanced research and developments. The only drawback is when the emphasis is on the theoretical part rather than the practical part. No one can deny that modern education is more effective with the help of Google, of course, when it comes to retention, understanding, and opportunities. The system should be made available to everyone so that each and every one can access it as per his or her interest. But, if Gurukul system has to comeback its objectives should be to prepare student in a manner that they do not just have the learning of the current training framework, but also beyond that. Millions of people around the world use search engine (Google) almost every day [9]. We actually gain a lot of benefits from it. But it also brings us harm. In ancient times when people met difficult things beyond their abilities, they often went for books or knowledgeable persons. But now-a-days we can simply put some key words in search box and then in less than second thousands of useful answers will show on the screen. So, by the above readings, we learn none of them; whether it is Gurukul or Google can stand alone for the better education system. That is why we need the power of both the systems. Together they stand as a better education system [10].

6. CONCLUSION

The Gurukul system of education has been in existence since ancient times. The Gurukuls' were supported by public donations. Gurukuls had limited number of teachers and students, while with the help of internet technology; we can increase the number of teachers and students. Google is internet based which lacks personal interactions; while on the other hand, Gurukuls were based on personal interaction between students and teacher. In Gurukul, teacher used to give one best opinion, but Google provide thousands of opinions, which might be difficult to compare and unnecessary and also consumes much of the time. Here, we have learned all about Gurukul its merits and demerits and about Google, its uses in today's modern world. And hence, we conclude that Gurukul and Google have its best ways in education. This calls for a combination of both type of system. Google emphasis only on the theoretical part rather than the practical part whereas Gurukul education focused on practical rather than theoretical part.so There must be an adjustment and a mix of both education system and convention if the overall development is to survive and affect today's general public. The objective of the authors is to prepare a new age Gurukul education in a manner that they do not just have the learning of the current training framework, but also beyond.

REFERENCES

1. Santhi, B., Girish G. Koundinya, and Jaikumar Ganesan. "Praagyah: Computer aided Gurukul System through Cloud Computing." *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* 5 (2013): 3223-26.
2. Shelly, Kusum Jain. "Relevance of Gurukul Education System in Present Circumstance: A Philosophical Perception." *education* 12 (2015).
3. Barahate, Yogini S. "Role of a teacher in imparting value-education." *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science* (2014): 13-15.
4. Gurukul, S. M. K. A., and B. N. Raju. "Isobaric Vapor-Liquid Equilibria of the 1-Propanol-n-Heptane System." *Journal of Chemical and Engineering Data* 11, no. 4 (1966): 501-502.
5. Brabazon, Tara. *The University of Google: Education in the (post) information age*. Routledge, 2016.
6. Joshi, Ankur, and Rajen K. Gupta. "Elementary education in Bharat (that is India): insights from a postcolonial ethnographic study of a Gurukul." *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management* 15, no. 1 (2017): 100-120.
7. Ross, Catherine E., and Barbara F. Reskin. "Education, control at work, and job satisfaction." *Social science research* 21, no. 2 (1992): 134-148.
8. Alexander, Robin J. *Culture and pedagogy: International comparisons in primary education*. Oxford: Blackwell, 2001.
9. Kashalkar-Karve, Sanyukta. "Comparitive study of ancient gurukul system and the new trends of Guru-Shishya Parampara." *American International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences* 2, no. 1 (2013): 81-84.
10. Gérard, Vergnaud. "A comprehensive theory of representation for mathematics education." *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior* 17, no. 2 (1998): 167-181.

CONTENTS		
1.	Vedic Period Gurukul vs Modern Period Google- The Two Varieties in the field of Education *Prakash Chandra Mishra	1-8
2.	THEORY OF PUNISHMENT AND SENTENCING *Parvati Rana	9-11
3.	Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility *Dr. Krishna Mukund	12-20
4.	भारत में धर्म की राजनीति *पूजा राय	21-25
5.	पर्यावरण एवं जनसंख्या *नीलम कुरील	26-28
6.	राँची नगर के उराँव जनजाति की सामाजिक-आर्थिक में परिवर्तन : एक समाजशास्त्रीय अध्ययन। *डॉ० गंगा केवट	29-31
7.	भारत में अनुसूचित जाति और सामाजिक न्याय की प्रासंगिकता *डा० अमिता रानी	32-45
8.	भारत में परिवार के बदलते स्वरूप *डा० आनन्द तनुजा	46-49
9.	राजस्थान में महिलाओं की सहभागिता की ऐतिहासिक पृष्ठभूमि तथा स्थिति एवं राजस्थान में सामाजिक चेतना *डॉ. सुमित्रा देवी शर्मा	50-56
10.	शिक्षा और समाज पर तकनीक का प्रभाव *डॉ. मुकेश कुमार मालवीय	57-59
11.	RIGHTS OF ACCUSED UNDER CONSTITUTION OF INDIA *Sachin	60-64
12.	A Comparative Study of Social Media Effect on Media (Special Reference to Madhya Pradesh Legislative Assembly Election 2018) *Dr. Pawan Singh Malik **Amarendra Kumar Aarya	65-75
13.	19वीं शताब्दी का बनारस *सपना यादव	76-78
